

Metal Halide-Phosphorus Halide-Alkyl Halide Complexes : Reactions with Boron(III), Aluminium(III) and Tin(IV) Chlorides

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Formation of stable solid complexes of boron trichloride, aluminium trichloride and tin tetrachloride with trichlorophosphine and phenyl dichlorophosphine in presence of alkylating agents such as *n*-butyl chloride, *sec*-butyl chloride, *iso*-butyl chloride, *tert*-amyl chloride, cyclohexyl chloride and triphenyl methyl chloride has been reported and the complexes have been characterized by vibrational spectroscopy as ionic species.

BULLOCK *et al.*¹ prepared ionic complexes from metal chloride trichloro or methyl dichlorophosphine and tertiary butyl chloride and determined the structure of the reaction products spectroscopically. We reported the reaction system metal chloride-phenyl dichlorophosphine alkyl chloride, $[MCl_x + PhPCl_2 + RCl]$ where $M = B, Al, Sn(IV)$ or $Fe(III)$ ^{2,3}. We extend our work using *n*-butyl chloride, *sec*-butyl chloride, *iso*-butyl chloride, *tert*-amyl chloride, cyclohexyl chloride and triphenyl methyl chloride as alkylating agents and trichlorophosphine and phenyl dichlorophosphine for the phosphonium cation. The isolated solid products were characterized by infrared spectroscopy which could readily be interpreted in terms of the cations $RR'PCl_2^+$ associated with one of the anions BCl_4^- , $AlCl_4^-$ and $SnCl_5^-$.

Experimental

Reagents : Boron trichloride (Hopkin and William Ltd.), anhydrous aluminium trichloride (BDH), trichlorophosphine (BDH) and triphenyl methyl chloride (Fluka) were used as supplied. *n*-Butyl chloride, *sec*-butyl chloride, *iso*-butyl chloride, *tert*-amyl chloride and cyclohexyl chloride were prepared, dried over P_2O_5 and distilled. Carbon disulphide (Pfizer) and methylene chloride (BDH) were dried over P_2O_5 and distilled before use. Tin tetrachloride was prepared by known laboratory method. Phenyl dichlorophosphine was synthesised by Buchner *et al.* method⁴.

Analysis : Chlorine was estimated by known gravimetric method. Aluminium was estimated as aluminium phosphate by the method described by Charlot *et al.*⁵. Tin was determined as oxide in presence of phosphorus. To estimate phosphorus, it was precipitated as magnesium ammonium phosphate after complexing the metal ions with excess of citric acid⁶.

Synthesis : Because of the hygroscopic nature of the reactants and products isolated here, all preparations were carried out under rigorous anhydrous conditions using all glass apparatus with inter-changeable standard joints. The order of addition was always kept the same to prevent the formation of hydrocarbon polymers. Excess of reagents were used to minimise the chance of polymeric anions formation. Preparation, products and analysis of the products are listed in Table I. The complexes melted in a wide range of temperature with decomposition above 200°.

(a) **Boron complexes :** The reactants and the solvents were cooled below 0° due to volatile nature and low boiling point of boron trichloride. A weighed quantity of boron trichloride was dissolved in carbon disulphide. To this solution, phosphine was added and the contents were shaken vigorously in order to have a homogenous solution. Keeping the temperature below 0°, the alkylating agent was introduced and mixed well. When the reaction mixture had attained the room temperature, the contents were allowed to stand. After some time, the solid product started separating and settled down. When the reaction had completed, the supernatant liquid was decanted and the complexes were washed with carbon disulphide and dried under vacuum (1-2 mm) at room temperature. The yield was 90 percent or more.

(b) **Aluminium complexes :**

(i) **Trichlorophosphine complexes :** To a weighed quantity of metal chloride suspended in carbon disulphide, trichlorophosphine was added and mixed well. Then the alkyl chloride was added and the contents were shaken well. After some time a white crystalline solid started separating. When all aluminium chloride had reacted, the mother liquor was decanted. The remaining solid was washed 2-3 times

TABLE—1

Sr. No.	\overline{MCl}_x	Reactants		R'	R	Product	Analysis					
		R'PCl ₂	RCI				Found % of			Calculated % of		
							M	P	Cl	M	P	Cl
Boron complexes												
1.	3.142	3.682	2.482	Cl	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^t PCl ₃] [BCl ₄]	-	8.46	70.96	3.11	8.92	71.50
2.	2.278	2.67	2.134	Cl	<i>tert</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	[Am ^t PCl ₃] [BCl ₄]	-	8.26	69.00	2.99	8.58	68.73
3.	2.346	2.749	2.374	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PCl ₃] [BCl ₄]	-	7.94	64.12	2.89	8.30	64.51
4.	2.226	2.609	5.299	Cl	Ph ₃ C	[Ph ₃ CPCl ₃] [BCl ₄]	-	5.57	46.82	2.027	5.81	46.54
5.	2.534	3.870	2.001	Ph	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^t PhPCl ₂] [BCl ₄]	-	7.68	54.71	2.79	7.97	54.72
6.	2.228	3.40	2.026	Ph	<i>tert</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	[Am ^t PhPCl ₂] [BCl ₄]	-	7.70	53.00	2.684	7.69	52.82
7.	2.764	4.222	2.797	Ph	C ₆ H ₁₁	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PhPCl ₂] [BCl ₄]	-	7.64	51.11	2.61	7.47	51.29
8.	2.114	3.229	5.029	Ph	Ph ₃ C	[Ph ₃ CPhPCl ₂] [BCl ₄]	-	5.29	37.01	1.88	5.39	36.99
Aluminium complexes												
9.	2.246	2.313	1.559	Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	7.24	8.12	68.00	7.43	8.53	68.32
10.	3.065	3.156	2.127	Cl	<i>sec</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	7.38	8.36	67.97	7.43	8.53	68.32
11.	2.867	2.952	1.990	Cl	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^t PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	7.52	8.66	68.44	7.43	8.53	68.32
12.	2.678	2.840	2.140	Cl	<i>tert</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	[Am ^t PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	7.28	8.09	65.47	7.15	8.21	65.78
13.	2.923	3.010	2.600	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	7.00	7.97	63.57	6.93	7.96	63.75
14.	2.734	2.815	5.716	Cl	Ph ₃ C	[Ph ₃ CPCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	5.08	5.58	45.61	4.91	5.64	45.17
15.	3.266	4.384	2.267	Ph	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	6.58	7.27	52.35	6.66	7.65	52.54
16.	2.632	3.533	1.827	Ph	<i>sec</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	6.72	7.59	52.68	6.66	7.65	52.54
17.	2.386	3.202	1.656	Ph	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	6.43	7.71	52.29	6.66	7.65	52.54
18.	2.129	2.857	1.701	Ph	<i>tert</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	[Am ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	6.36	7.42	51.00	6.44	7.39	50.78
19.	2.792	3.747	2.209	Ph	C ₆ H ₁₁	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	6.25	7.13	49.64	6.26	7.19	49.36
20.	2.624	3.522	5.486	Ph	Ph ₃ C	[Ph ₃ CPhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	4.78	5.00	35.89	4.56	5.24	35.99
Tin complexes												
21.	3.214	1.694	1.42	Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PCl ₃] [SnCl ₆]	24.75	6.29	57.82	24.20	6.32	57.83
22.	3.178	1.675	1.129	Cl	<i>sec</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PCl ₃] [SnCl ₆]	24.39	6.12	58.02	24.20	6.32	57.83
23.	2.818	1.518	1.001	Cl	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^t PCl ₃] [SnCl ₆]	24.48	6.25	57.59	24.20	6.32	57.83
24.	4.016	2.117	1.643	Cl	<i>tert</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	[Am ^t PCl ₃] [SnCl ₆]	24.00	6.41	56.35	23.53	6.14	56.23
25.	4.125	2.174	1.878	Cl	C ₆ H ₁₁	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PCl ₃] [SnCl ₆]	23.07	6.09	55.18	22.98	5.99	54.92
26.	2.268	1.195	2.427	Cl	Ph ₃ C	[Ph ₃ CPCl ₃] [SnCl ₆]	17.65	4.74	41.57	17.54	4.58	41.92
27.	3.564	2.448	1.266	Ph	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PhPCl ₂] [SnCl ₆]	22.64	5.68	46.46	22.31	5.82	46.64
28.	3.329	2.287	1.182	Ph	<i>sec</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^s PhPCl ₂] [SnCl ₆]	22.42	5.84	47.01	22.21	5.82	46.64
29.	2.872	1.973	1.020	Ph	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	[Bu ^t PhPCl ₂] [SnCl ₆]	22.17	5.49	46.78	22.21	5.82	46.64
30.	3.414	2.345	1.396	Ph	<i>tert</i> -C ₆ H ₁₁	[Am ^t PhPCl ₂] [SnCl ₆]	21.58	5.76	45.04	21.73	5.67	45.44
31.	4.178	2.870	1.902	Ph	C ₆ H ₁₁	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PhPCl ₂] [SnCl ₆]	21.21	5.45	44.63	21.27	5.55	44.47
32.	2.633	1.809	2.817	Ph	Ph ₃ C	[Ph ₃ CPhPCl ₂] [SnCl ₆]	16.25	4.34	34.65	16.52	4.31	34.55

with carbon disulphide and dried at room temperature and under reduced pressure. Nearly 80 percent yield was obtained in each case.

(ii) *Phenyl dichlorophosphine complexes* : Phenyl dichlorophosphine was added to aluminium chloride suspended in 40 ml of methylene chloride and the contents were shaken well in order to dissolve the aluminium chloride. Then alkyl chloride was added. The contents were shaken occasionally and allowed to stand. Finally white coloured crystalline solid started separating. On completion of reaction, the

liquid portion was decanted and the solid was washed with the solvent. Dried the solid under reduced pressure (2 mm) at 25° (yield 90 percent and more).

(c) *Tin complexes* : Tin(IV) chloride was dissolved in 30-40 ml of methylene chloride and phosphines were added to this solution. Mixed the contents well and then, alkyl chloride was added. The reaction vessel was closed and set aside until precipitation of the reaction products had ceased. The supernatant liquid was transferred to another flask

and the residue, white crystalline solids, were washed 2-3 times with the solvent by decantation. The products, were dried in vacuo for about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hour at room temperature, yield was more than 80 percent.

Spectroscopy: Infra-red spectra of the complexes in spectral region $4000-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Samples were prepared in nujol mull between potassium bromide plates. The spectra for the region $500-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were taken from I.I.T., New Delhi.

Results and Discussion

The products isolated in the present investigation were fairly sensitive to moisture and became sticky when exposed to atmosphere. The complexes obtained from phenyl dichlorophosphine were better in yield than those from trichlorophosphine. The formation of the products also depended upon the reactivity of alkylating agents which has the order triphenyl methyl chloride > *tert*-amyl chloride > cyclohexyl chloride > *iso*-butyl chloride > *sec*-butyl chloride > *n*-butyl chloride. With benzyl chloride and allyl chloride some black products were obtained which on analysis gave no definite composition.

The compounds were soluble only in acetone but were not recoverable as such on removal of solvent suggesting that they dissociated in solution. With conclusions from vibrational spectral analysis and elemental analytical data the complexes were taken to be univalent ionic species.

Cation spectra: Phosphorus in tetra covalent compounds has tetrahedral structure. The penta atomic molecules with general formula XY_3Z are expected to have six vibrational modes, all of which are infrared active⁷. The absorption bands between $790-780\text{ cm}^{-1}$, in the vibrational spectra of the compounds containing alkyl trichlorophosphonium cations, could be attributed to P-C (alkyl) vibration. P-Cl vibrations were observed in the form of very strong and shoulder absorption between $645-630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and between $490-475\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Absorption bands between $215-208\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were weak and may be assigned to R'-P-Cl vibrations. These values agree well to the literature values^{1,8}. The alkyl trichlorophosphonium cations, $[\text{R}'\text{PCl}_3]^+$, is expected to have distorted tetrahedral structure having C_{3v} symmetry.

Alkyl phenyl dichlorophosphonium cation should be further distorted tetrahedrally, having $6A'$ and $3A''$ vibrational modes. Penta atomic molecules of this type have C_s symmetry. In agreement to our earlier results^{2,8}, the infrared spectra showed very strong absorptions at $1450-1435\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1005-990\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to P-Ph [A' (P-C)] vibrations. Seel *et al*⁹ also observed similar bands at 1439 cm^{-1} and 998 cm^{-1} respectively. Absorptions between

$795-785\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ms to vs) were due to P-alkyl [A' (P-C)] vibrations. Bands obtained in the region $615-605\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $508-472\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $A''\nu\text{P-Cl}$ and $A'\nu\text{P-C}$ vibrations.

Anion spectra: In the anions BCl_4^- , absorptions at about 1090 cm^{-1} and 1030 cm^{-1} were assigned to $\nu_1 + \nu_3$ combination modes. Other observed bands nearly at $990, 875, 720, 675, 385$ and 285 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu_2 + \nu_3, \nu_3, \nu_1 + \nu_4, \nu_1,$ and ν_4 respectively. The bands at $500-490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $310-305\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were very weak, broad and of doubtful nature, which may be assigned to $\nu_3 - \nu_2$ and $\nu_3 - \nu_1$. There may be some distortion of tetrahedral T_d symmetry due to appearance of ν_1 at $390-380\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Similar to BCl_4^- ion, AlCl_4^- has also tetrahedral structure. The vibrational spectra of the compound containing this anion agree well with the results reported earlier^{11,2}. The strong bands at $850-845\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_1 + \nu_3$. The absorption band attributable to $\nu_1 + \nu_4$ was observed in shoulder and medium weak form nearly at 530 cm^{-1} . Other bands were at 495 cm^{-1} (sh) and 555 cm^{-1} (ms) could be assigned to $\nu_3 - \nu_3$.

As reported earlier SnCl_4 forms the anion SnCl_5^- , instead of SnCl_6^{2-} , confirmed by elemental analysis and i.r. spectral data^{1,2}. The presence of metal-halogen stretching frequency nearly at $340\text{ cm}^{-1}(\nu_1)$ further supports the penta-coordination of tin as suggested by Beattie *et al*¹⁰ (for a given oxidation state of a metal, these frequencies decrease with increase in coordination number). The SnCl_5^- anion may have trigonal bipyramidal structure with D_{3h} symmetry.

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References

1. J. I. BULLOCK, F. W. PERRETT and N. J. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1972, 1843.
2. D. M. PURI and M. S. SAINI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 362.
3. D. M. PURI and M. S. SAINI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977
4. B. BUCHNER, and L. B. LOCKHART, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 755.
5. G. CHARLOT and D. BEZIER, 'Quantitative Inorganic Analysis' Methuen & Co. Ltd., London, Translated by R. C. Murray, R. C. Murray, edn. 1957, p. 325.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., 3rd Edn. 1961, p. 574.
7. S. D. ROSS, "Inorganic Infrared and Raman Spectra" McGraw Hill, London, edn. 1972, chap. 7.
8. I. R. BEATTIE, K. LIVINGSTON and T. GILSON, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1968, 1.
9. F. SEEL, K. BALLREICH and R. SCHMUTZLER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, 94, 1173.
10. I. R. BEATTIE, T. R. GILSON, K. LIVINGSTON, V. FAWCETT and G. OZIN, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1967, 712.